

GENOMED4ALL USE CASE META DATA

AVAILABLE FOR OPEN SCIENCE

The GenoMed4ALL project

Accumulating evidence points towards personalised medicine to treat and manage common, rare and ultra-rare haematological diseases. Advanced statistics and machine learning approaches may contribute to the exploitation of omics and clinical data in patient-oriented research and decision-making. [GenoMed4ALL is an European project](#), funded under the call “Societal Challenges - Health, demographic change and well-being” with grant agreement ID: 101017549, with start date 1 January 2021 and end date 30 June 2025.

GenoMed4ALL aims to demonstrate the potential and benefits of trustable and explainable AI technologies to exploit the powerful set of “omics” data for advancing research and personalized medicine. The use cases are three Haematological Diseases (HDs), oncological and non-oncological. HDs involve a class of up to 450 disorders in six large groups. The overall number of patients affected with haematological malignancies account about 5% of cancers. Most HDs can cause chronic health problems and many of them are life-threatening conditions requiring numerous resources and multidisciplinary teams, thus representing a public health challenge.

The use cases:

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS)

Multiple Myeloma (MM)

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

Multiple Myeloma (MM)

The Disease

Multiple Myeloma (MM) is a type of bone marrow cancer originating in plasma cells, a type of white blood cell responsible for producing antibodies to fight off infections. In patients with MM, cancerous plasma cells accumulate in the bone marrow and produce abnormal proteins instead, which can lead to decreased blood cell numbers, bone and kidney damage.

Clinical Aims

Understand Disease Complexity	Describe the different layers of MM heterogeneity integrating baseline genomic and imaging data.
Identify Evolution Dynamics	Define the quantitative and qualitative dynamics of the disease in time.
Study Risk Progression	Develop a prognostic risk score for the baseline and the disease remaining after therapy.
Integrate Radiomics and Radiogenomics	Develop and validate a model to predict treatment response and determine progression-free survival.

Data

Baseline clinical data and whole genome Copy Number Alterations (CNAs) landscape data, as detected by Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) array and Ultra-Low Pass Whole Genome Sequencing (ULP-WGS) from 253 patients.

Liquid biopsy data and imaging data (PET-CT) at baseline from 82 patients.

All patients received induction therapy, for which 164 undergo bone marrow transplant, 113 went through consolidation therapy and 145 sustained maintenance therapy. The therapy classes used were Immunomodulatory (IMiD) based ("Rev-Dex", "TD", "VRD", "LENA", "MPT", "RD", "CTD", "VTD", "MPT", "MPR", "KRD", "IRD", "ERD", "DRD", "PD", "PVD", "EPD", "ISAPD", "DPD"), Protein Inhibitors (PI) based ("VEL", "VD", "VMP", "VCD", "VTD", "PAD", "VMP", "DVTD", "DVD", "KD", "KCD", "KRD", "ISAKD", "IRD"), or a combination of the two.

Clinical and genomic data from 750 patients available from public repositories (1A12 release CoMMpass database).

Study design: Retrospective study

Specific objectives

- **Understand Disease Complexity:** Describe the different layers of MM heterogeneity integrating baseline genomic and imaging data.
- **Identify Evolution Dynamics:** Define the quantitative and qualitative dynamics of the disease in time.
- **Study Risk Progression:** Develop a prognostic risk score for the baseline and the disease remaining after therapy.
- **Integrate Radiomics and Radiogenomics:** Develop and validate a model to predict treatment response and determine progression-free survival.

Study Population

- A 1st cohort of 82 Newly Diagnosed Multiple Myeloma patients. For each patient, the following data have been provided: baseline clinical data, imaging data (PET-CT), i.e. as number, volumes and scores of medullary and extramedullary lesions, liquid biopsy data, i.e. tumour fraction of cell-free DNA (cfDNA), which indicates DNA from cells that have died as a result of high cell proliferation in tumour lesions or therapy, measures of CNAs related to the tumour CD138+, response to therapy and outcome (patients underwent different treatments and have a median follow-up of 26 months). Tumour fraction of cfDNA and genomic data were obtained through ULP-WGS. Patients included in the study have been up-front treated with combination regimens including the so-called “novel drugs” (PI, IMiD, monoclonal antibodies) and either autologous stem cell transplantation (< 65 years old patients) or continuous therapy (> 65 years old patients).
- A 2nd cohort of 171 newly diagnosed Multiple Myeloma patients. For each patient, the following data have been provided: baseline clinical data, measures of CNAs related to the tumour CD138+ clone by SNP array, response to therapy and outcome.

- Clinical and genomic data from 750 MM patients available from public repositories (1A12 release CoMMpass database).

Clinical Partners

1. NKUA (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens)
2. UNIBO (Università di Bologna)
3. ICH (Humanitas Mirasole)

About the data

MM data provide a comprehensive resource for studying MM progression, treatment response, and minimal residual disease (MRD) assessment. It includes baseline clinical data and whole-genome copy number alteration (CNA) profiles, detected via SNP arrays enabling the identification of genomic instability patterns associated with disease progression. Additionally, clinical and genomic data from both bone marrow clones and liquid biopsies, alongside PET-CT and whole-body MRI imaging at baseline, are available for a subset of patients, facilitating a multimodal approach to disease characterization. These patients also have NGS and imaging (PET-CT and WB-MRI) MRD data, providing critical insights into treatment efficacy and disease persistence at a minimal residual level. Furthermore, clinical and genomic data are accessible through public repositories, including the CoMMpass database, allowing for large-scale comparative analyses. Lastly, the dataset includes information on newly diagnosed patients undergoing induction therapy supporting investigations into treatment responses and long-term patient outcomes.

Metadata

In the file Genomed4All_MM_Use_Case_Metadata.xls metadata from MM use case are reported, as the following excerpt.

→ CLINICAL METADADA (1)

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE
MPC	Patient identification code	character
gDNA_sample_sheet_ID	DNA baseline sequencing experiment ID	character
gDNA_tumor_fraction	Genomic DNA purity baseline	num
cfDNA_tumor_fraction	Circulating DNA purity baseline	num
PET_POS_NEG	Negative patients have Bone Marrow Deauville Score = 2 and Focal Lesion Impetus criteria =1. The remaining patients are scored as positive	factor
BM_DS	Bone Marrow Deauville Score	factor
BM_DS_M_4	Bone Marrow Deauville Score >= 4	factor
BM_Suv_max	Bone Marrow Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num
FL_sec_Impetus	Focal Lesion Impetus (Italian myeloma criteria for PET use) Score	factor
FL_DS	Focal Lesion Deauville Score	factor
FL_DS_M_4	Focal Lesion Deauville Score >= 4	factor
FL_SUV_max	Focal Lesion Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num

Excerpt from Clinical Metadata

Aggregated Data

Some summary characteristics of the cohort to which the metadata refer are reported in the file "Genomed4All_MM_Use_Case_aggregated_data.xls"